

THE IMPORTANCE OF GENDER EQUALITY IN MODERN SOCIETY

¹Sadikova Y.S., ²Khusanova Kh.Sh.

¹Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov, Department of Public Law, Faculty of Law, Head of Department, Candidate of Legal Sciences

²Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov, Faculty of Law, Group 104 Student
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14565801>

Abstract. *This article discusses the critical issue of gender equality in modern society, the ongoing reforms, and legislative changes in this area, along with references to legal sources.*

Keywords: *Gender equality, law, President, Constitution, states, normative-legal documents.*

Gender equality, ensuring equal opportunities and rights for both men and women, is a fundamental value for any society. This concept is crucial not only for women but also for men, as it plays a significant role in social justice and human rights. Gender equality is considered a core value in any society, addressing important human rights and social justice issues. It is essential for both women and men, as it ensures the expected social changes and addresses various issues in society.

Gender equality is one of the principles of social justice. It ensures that all genders have equal opportunities in economic, political, and social spheres, helping every individual in society to realize their full potential. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has paid special attention to gender equality issues, highlighting the importance of protecting women's rights and supporting their participation in social and political life. For instance, he emphasized providing women with equal opportunities in all fields, encouraging their education and employment. He stressed that ensuring gender equality contributes significantly to societal development.

On March 8, 2021, during an event dedicated to International Women's Day, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev discussed the role of women and the opportunities provided to them. He also pointed out the measures to ensure gender equality under the program "Support for Women" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Gender equality promotes social justice, allowing men and women to realize their full potential. Attention is also being given to gender equality in economic development, as involving women in economic activities helps support the nation's growth.

Gender equality leads to new ideas and innovations in society. Women's participation in political life makes the decision-making process more democratic and helps take into account the interests of various segments of society.

However, challenges remain in achieving gender equality. Women often face issues such as discrimination, lower wages compared to men in workplaces, and limited opportunities for career advancement. Women and men also have different health care needs. Ensuring gender equality helps allocate health services and resources equally for all.

Globally, many efforts have been made towards gender equality, yet achieving full equality remains a significant challenge. The United Nations has declared one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 5) for 2030 to ensure gender equality. Many countries are developing laws and policies to promote gender equality. In Uzbekistan, measures are being implemented to

protect women's rights, promote women's economic independence, and improve the education system.

Here is the translation into English:

In modern society, there are countries with a high level of gender equality. Examples include:

Scandinavian Countries (Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Finland):

Political and Social Policies: The governments of Scandinavian countries pay great attention to ensuring gender equality. They have developed laws and policies aimed at promoting women's participation in the workforce, ensuring gender equality, and distributing family responsibilities more equitably.

Canada:

Political Participation: Canada has strategies focused on gender equality in politics, including programs aimed at supporting women in politics and ensuring gender equality.

Equal Opportunities and Fair Pay: Canada emphasizes achieving pay equity between men and women, as both genders often perform the same types of work, and it is considered fair that they receive equal salaries.

Netherlands:

In the Netherlands, numerous laws exist to create equal opportunities for men and women. The Dutch government encourages women's active participation in politics and the workforce and has implemented laws against sexual and domestic violence.

However, there are also countries where gender equality is very low. These include:

Yemen:

Limited Opportunities: Women in Yemen are deprived of many social, political, and economic rights. Opportunities for women to work or participate in politics are extremely limited. Women are often confined to household chores and family obligations.

Afghanistan:

In Afghanistan, women play a very limited role in government and social life. Since the Taliban came to power in 2021, women's opportunities for employment and political participation have been further restricted. Additionally, women's access to education is almost completely denied, and they are not allowed to go outside alone. If they do leave home, they must be accompanied by a male relative.

Sudan:

In Sudan, the role of women in life is often dictated by men. There are few laws to protect women, and patriarchal views dominate the upbringing of women. Political participation, education, and economic opportunities for women are restricted. Moreover, physical and psychological violence against women is prevalent.

Gender equality is not only an issue of social rights but also the foundation of a society's economic and political development. There is a growing global understanding of this. Every country must develop gender equality policies that align with its social, cultural, and economic conditions. Creating equal opportunities for women and men can enhance individual well-being and significantly contribute to the social and economic development of the entire society.

In conclusion, gender equality is a fundamental element of sustainable development and social justice in any society. This issue plays a vital role in the political and economic systems of every country on a global scale.

Scandinavian countries and some other developed nations have achieved significant progress in gender equality. However, many developing and underdeveloped countries still face challenges in this regard. Low levels of gender equality are especially prevalent in patriarchal societies and countries where traditional views dominate.

Protective laws for women, access to education and economic opportunities, as well as combating discrimination against gender inequality, are essential measures to address these challenges. To ensure gender equality in the future, more social and political reforms need to be implemented in all countries.

Only then can societies achieve true equality, foster economic growth, and ensure sustainable prosperity. Gender equality not only benefits women but also enables all members of society to participate equally in social and economic activities, which, in turn, is a critical step toward building a more just and stable state.

REFERENCES

1. United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Goal 5: Gender Equality
Source: United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.
2. "Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment". A report by the UN on women's rights and gender equality.
3. Annual Reports on Gender Equality by the World Economic Forum. Source: *The Global Gender Gap Report*.
4. "*The State of the World's Children*" by UNICEF, focusing on children's rights, education, and gender equality.
5. "*Gender Equality: Striving for Justice in an Unequal World*" by Ruth Lister, an analytical work on gender equality.
6. "*The Second Sex*" by Simone de Beauvoir, a classic work on gender and women's rights.
7. Decree and Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in 2017. Focused on supporting women and ensuring gender equality.
8. Election Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan.